

TECHNOLOGIES FOR WORKING WITH GIFTED BLIND CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article provides ideas on how to help visually impaired children develop their talents.*

Keywords: *blind, talent, intellect, individual, technology, pedagogy.*

Introduction

In our country, large-scale work is being carried out in the field of state policy regarding youth. "The fact that our youth are rightfully able to take responsibility for the future of our country and are becoming the decisive force of today and tomorrow gives us all pride and honor." Such reliable opinions of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev about the youth of our country encourage us, educators, to take a serious approach to forming the spirituality of a perfect generation, developing the interest of every student in the profession and educating them in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland. In today's fast-paced world, high demands are placed on human activity in various spheres of society. It is important for a specialist to have great creative opportunities in the conditions where important reforms are being implemented in every aspect of social life. In connection with this, the role and importance of the school and the teacher, especially the elementary school teacher, in the formation of the student's creative abilities and the realization of potential opportunities increases. It is impossible to raise the educational process to a qualitatively new level without completely updating the content of education in the modern school, without identifying and developing the creativity and talent of students. The field of pre-school education, being the first link of the continuous education system, plays an important role in preparing a child for school in the key education system. Today, it is no coincidence that this field of education has risen to the level of state policy. In this regard, it is known to everyone that a number of decrees, decisions and orders adopted by our state are aimed at the fundamental reform of the preschool education system.

Research materials and methodology

Studying the specific features of the influence of education on the development of children's talent is traditionally considered one of the most important psychological and pedagogical tasks. Psychological-pedagogical theory and educational practice have always announced the task of monitoring children's talent, early identification, comprehensive development of children's talents and abilities, and expressed the desire to solve the problems of special education of gifted children. The importance of working with gifted children is determined by several factors: public awareness of "human potential" is understood as the most important condition and the main source of its development. Acceleration of life dynamics, increase of information and emotional loads for a person, various problems that require enormous intellectual efforts to solve state the demand for making talented children creative, active, social, responsible and highly educated.

The Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan: starting from 2021, at least once a year, organizes competitions among talented young people who are engaged in scientific and innovative activities in the republic within the framework of the "Future scientist" and "Academic mobility" programs;

In the organization of sending talented young people to foreign higher education institutions and scientific organizations on the basis of a short-term competition, the supervision of the implementation of this decision shall be entrusted to the advisor of the Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the head of the department of technologies, telecommunications and innovative activities O.M. Umarov and the Minister of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.Yu Abdurakhmanov.

In our country, attention is paid to the support of educated and talented young people and their spiritual maturity at the level of state policy. In the process of intensive reforms, normative and legal documents supporting them in all spheres are being adopted in order to strengthen the legal foundations of state policy regarding youth. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 30, 2020 "On measures to fundamentally reform the youth policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and take it to a new level" has a special place in this. This, in turn, is of great importance in ensuring the active participation of young people in the life of the state and society, in raising a mature generation that is highly moral, independent and free-thinking, thoroughly assimilating the achievements of modern science.

Discussion and results

Studying the specific characteristics of the influence of education on the development of children's talent is traditionally considered one of the most important psychological and pedagogical tasks. Psychological-pedagogical theory and educational practice have always announced the task of monitoring children's talent, early detection, comprehensive development of children's talents and abilities, and expressed the desire to solve special educational problems of gifted children.

The relevance of working with gifted children is determined by several conditions: "Human potential" is understood as the awareness of society, the most important condition and the main source of its development.

Acceleration of life dynamics, increase of information and emotional loads for a person, various problems that require great intellectual efforts to solve; The requirements for professional activities, higher education and pedagogical work of a person who should be creative, active, socially responsible, highly educated, etc. with gifted children have a special place in the formation of such a person.

The model of free development of a gifted child in the conditions of additional education is a system of psychological and pedagogical support that implements various diagnostic programs for the needs of children, parents, and the needs of regions. Self-development and self-education, student's creative conditions, set of didactic conditions and didactic process project.

The practical significance of the research is to determine the composition of psychological and pedagogical support for the education of a gifted child in additional general education and the development of a gifted child. Its results have radically new features leading education of children and adolescents with non-traditional educational projects. They can be used for high-quality analysis of work practices with gifted children in any region. Methodological recommendations of

psychological and pedagogical support developed within the program can be used for pedagogical activity of teachers and their retraining.

Forms for identifying gifted children:

Tracking;

Communication with parents;

Olympiads, competitions, scientific-practical conferences;

The work of a psychologist and teacher is: testing, asking questions, interviewing. The principles of pedagogical activity in working with gifted children are as follows:

The principle of the maximum variety of opportunities provided for personal development;

The principle of increasing the role of extracurricular activities;

The principle of individualization and differentiation of training:

Expected result:

1. Improvement of the system of identification, support and development of gifted children;
2. Creation of a data bank on students in the categories of gifted: intellectual, creative, sports.

In the modern world, it is difficult for teachers to identify a truly gifted child, because for this it is necessary to conduct a series of tests. Gifted children require special attention from parents, teachers, peers and other members of society. It depends on recognizing the child's talent and whether it will be fully revealed.

Identification of gifted children, development of their abilities is one of the tasks of a civilized society. Formation of well-rounded human personality is one of the urgent problems of our time. Because the future of our Motherland directly depends on the education, potential, talent and independent thinking of today's young generation. That is why the task of educating knowledgeable, broad-minded people has been raised to the priority level of the state policy. As the Honorable President noted, "concern about the future generation, striving to raise a healthy and well-rounded generation, is our national characteristics".

Today, along with healthy teenagers, the educational process of visually impaired peers is organized at the high level, taking into account the physical and mental capabilities of the blind, so that they can become people who serve our country.

Studying the emotional characteristics of visually impaired adolescents is one of the important issues. Because according to the "National Personnel Training Program" and the Law "On Education" adopted in our Republic, great attention is paid to the formation of high consciousness, independent thinking in children, and to impart knowledge specific to their mental qualities.

In the history of education, our thinkers attached great importance to the study of scientific knowledge in the education of a well-rounded person. Each created pamphlet, each educational and ethical work has a certain value in terms of its own education and training. Therefore, in these works, the goals and means of perfecting Islam in terms of mental, moral, and physical aspects, various styles and methods are expressed. The ways of educating others are described. Therefore, it is necessary to teach students to think, to develop their thinking, and to increase their interest in learning in the process of choosing examples from educational and moral works. At the same time, the use of methods such as scientific discussion, interpretive learning, problem solving, observation, question-and-answer, knowledge testing, and demonstration experiments, which are suitable for teaching, will give good results.

Nowadays, knowledge is delivered to everyone in the form of ready-made information. As a result, children are bored in classes and their interest in learning is decreasing. With the use of past educational experience, educational methods should be focused on showing the abilities of each student, sharpening his mind, and developing his thinking. As a result, it is better to separate excellent, good, and average students and conduct training with them in a unique individual way.

It is necessary to increase the amount of knowledge given to gifted students and pay more attention to their independent engagement with literature. Talented students should have the opportunity to graduate early after mastering the amount of knowledge required in school education and passing a certain test.

It is important for every teacher to introduce the secrets of art and problem-solving skills to students along with general knowledge.

It is necessary to pay great attention to education of students' minds, strengthening of knowledge, long-term retention, and development of thinking ability. For this purpose, such methods as solving chistons (riddles), interpreting and commenting on a literary work stimulate the student and increase his interest in reading.

From the history of education, it became known that in the mental education of every person, great attention is paid to the education of thought, the development of thinking, and the education of the mind. In schools and madrassas, the aim is increasing the logical thinking of students to develop their independent activities and creative abilities. The methods and ways related to the development of ingenuity, speed of understanding, mental sharpness, the ability to quickly acquire knowledge, quick understanding of problems, the ability to memorize, and strengthening memory are especially noteworthy. For this, suitable teaching methods were also chosen. Methods such as scientific discussion, interpretive study, problem solving, and testing were used, and educational methods helped each student to show his abilities, sharpen his mind, and develop his thinking. As a result, excellent, good, and average learners were distinguished, and training with them was conducted in a way that took into account their unique, individual characteristics. In groups, the amount of knowledge given to gifted children was increased, and after a certain test, they had the opportunity to graduate from school or madrasa, even before the deadline.

Activity in the educational process leads the student to deep and solid acquisition of knowledge, to demonstrate his abilities. Activity to knowledge ensures intellectual development of the student.

A person's social activity and ability is the guarantee of all his success. Because every person becomes active only with his own work, enthusiasm, and desire. No matter how well the teacher teaches or educates, if the student does not try, the development will not be successful. After all, the main reason for all spiritual and moral deficiencies is that a person does not conduct his activities in the right way. In the content of every event planned in educational institutions, clubs, love for the Motherland and perfect human education should be reflected. It is possible to attract talented individuals and talented young people to various circles in educational institutions, taking into account their unique psychological aspects and qualities, in cooperation with the employees of the "Talent Center of the Republic" and using their scientific and practical experience to identify their talents. In self-management of students during the period of independent training, the pedagogue conducts work with students in a differentiated way, divides them into groups, and works with some of them individually.

In modern psychology, two terms have been created based on the word "Gift": "Children with signs of giftedness" and "Childhood talent".

The term "gifted children" refers to a special group of children who are usually ahead of their peers in development.

The second term - "Children's talent" indicates that each person has a certain intellectual and creative potential. According to this concept, two global problems arise in psychology and later in the theory of education, and they come from the same root.

Development of psychological foundations and creation of a system of development and support of gifted and talented children;

Development of psychological foundations and practical measures aimed at developing the intellectual and creative potential of each child in the field of education.

Each of these tasks requires solving four problems relatively independently:

- Defining the concept of talent;
- Development of a talent diagnosis model;
- Determining the basis for predicting the development of children with signs of giftedness;
- Creating a comprehensive system of development and support of children's talent in the field of education.

Later, on this basis, a general scheme of psychodiagnostic work and methodological tools is developed. The results obtained at the diagnostic stage are the basis for verifying the development of the individual. All this modeling of the development process serves as a basis for the development of theoretical foundations and practice of education.

Separate diagnostics in educational practice cannot solve the problem of predicting the development of talent. Episodic diagnosis does not allow to objectively solve not only the problem of determining the level of children's talent, but also the problem of predicting development. The reason for this is the autonomy of diagnostic, prognostic and developmental processes.

The internal concept of talent provides a single theoretical basis for studying the phenomenon of talent (definitions of talent, classification of its types, methods of identification, etc.).

Talent is a systematic quality of the psyche that develops throughout life and determines a person's ability to achieve high (unusual, outstanding) results in one or more types of activities compared to other people.

A child with signs of giftedness is a child who is distinguished by bright, clear, sometimes amazing achievements (or has internal conditions for such achievements) in one or another activity.

Signs of giftedness are the characteristics of a gifted child that are manifested in the actual activity and can be evaluated at the level of observing the nature of his actions.

The characteristics of specific talent are defined in its definition and are associated with high performance. At the same time, the child's talent should be evaluated in the unity of the "I want" and "I can" categories. Therefore, signs of giftedness cover two aspects of the behavior of a gifted child: instrumental (describes the ways of activity) and motivational (describes the child's attitude to activity).

In our opinion, special attention should be paid to the issue of the practice of working with gifted children who need special support.

The analysis of research conducted by foreign experts allows us to distinguish three educational strategies: children with a strong growth in mental development study according to the standard school curriculum at a pace that corresponds to their individual capabilities enabling acceleration; enrichment provides expansion and deepening of the content of the studied material; grouping involves grouping gifted children into interest groups for learning in different curricula and programs.

A gifted child is a harmonious combination of relationships: communicative, intellectual, informational, emotional and personal. Ignoring any aspect of a child's relationship affects the harmony of his development. Practical scientific analysis shows that high intellect or academic ability does not guarantee success not only in adulthood, but also in the process of studying at school. Therefore, it is very important that didactic constructions come from understanding the diversity and complexity of the gifted child's personality. Therefore, the educational process for gifted children requires the creation of a special educational environment.

This developing environment combines various educational credos, their elements, educational material and subjects of the educational process as the central part of the educational process. The most difficult thing is to harmoniously form the subjectivity of the teacher and the gifted child, because the student cannot automatically become the subject of educational activities. The student's transformation into a subject occurs in the course of educational activities, and it should be remembered that the process of accumulating subjective experience is a non-linear process. This creates some difficulties in understanding the dynamics of development of a gifted child as a teacher. After all, the teacher also develops as a subject of pedagogical activity.

The holistic realization of personal abilities develops in connection with the transformation of opportunities into clearly embodied actions of a positive character.

Based on their abilities, interests, and inclinations, each student is given the opportunity to learn, study, and be educated in the class of groups based on their educational interests in various clubs and special courses.

Abandoning pre-planning of educational activities, forming and developing critical creative thinking in students, forcing them to think creatively, come up with new ideas, change the attitude to education, make them achieve success is the main factor in motivation. The missing factor in educational activities is creativity. More than 830 non-governmental non-commercial organizations and public associations that protect the interests of young people are operating in the republic. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan announced "Five important initiatives".

Spiritual and educational work and working with talented young people, especially students - working with young people, relying on the national idea and the national program of personnel training, by establishing democratic principles based on national and universal values , human rights - implement a long-term, large-scale spiritual and moral education program aimed at glorifying his dignity, raising a physically healthy, mentally mature, deep-minded and independent thinking person.

Independent observation is the only correct way to study in boarding schools for blind children. Only in this way can people with vision problems acquire the basic concepts that form the foundation for learning. Only through independent observation can they draw correct conclusions about objects and the relationship between them. This increases the self-confidence of the blind child. When introducing the object, the teacher should ensure that the object is in the hands of each blind child. Otherwise, the child learns not the body, but the teacher's understanding

of the body. In this case, the student will be deprived of the opportunity to easily absorb, analyze and research new information in his own way. In the process of studying the body, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the child can make it. Because the potential of being able to reconstruct each studied thing with the help of imagination is proof that the student has correctly accepted the subject. Color and paint do not exist for him, but he has an inner power that makes the world of fantasy rich, beautiful and clear, which the seeing child did not even dream of. This is a creative imagination. It is this quality that awakens a creative genius, a great poet and a fine musicologist in the heart of a child, and enables a worthy life.

While practical work gives the child the opportunity to work independently, to form a correct image of the body, some children with visual impairments have the mentality of "I can't do it alone", "What will I do if I break it", "If I don't get it, it will be a shame" that forms the ability to work independently and apply theoretically acquired knowledge in practice.

Conclusion

Literature and art, which play an important role in human life, require a certain amount of talent to create images and portray them in different situations. In addition, activity, hard work, unwavering action towards a certain goal is required.

Parents of gifted children should be in constant contact with a psychologist. The reason is that family members may not have noticed that their child is talented. It is advisable for parents to choose which club they want to attend based on their child's interest and talent, in consultation with the school psychologist. When choosing a gifted student, the psychologist must first of all increase the child's self-confidence and inspire.

Every child has his own talent. Someone is interested in painting, someone is interested in singing, and another is interested in writing poetry. Talent in a person first appears as ability. The earlier it is identified and developed in the child, the more will he grow into a mature person in the future. If it is not paid attention to, it can become incapacitating.

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